

AN ANALYSIS ON THE PERSONNEL SATISFACTION WITH REFERENCE TO SELECTED RESORTS OF ALAPPUZHA DISTRICT, KERALA

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Abstract

Job satisfaction is one of the important factors of the organizations to enhance the productivity of employee. Personnel satisfaction is one of the critical criteria to improve the efficiency of any organizations. There is a usual saying “Happy workers are productive workers and productive workers are likely to be happy”. Here the researchers have selected the employees working in various resorts in Alappuzha District, Kerala to conduct the research. The Researchers have taken an attempt to understand the level of personnel satisfaction of the employee of selected resorts in Alappuzha District, Kerala. The data is collected by using primary data and secondary data. For primary data collection a schedule comprising 22 questions divided into 3 major segments were used. Convenience sampling technique is used to get a final sample of 140 by rejecting 10 samples due to lack of clarity. For analysis, simple percentage analysis method was used.

Key words: Personnel satisfaction, work environment, job satisfaction, organizational climate, etc.

1. Introduction

The tourism industry is one of the prominent service sectors in the country. The sector generates immense employment opportunities for the people and also acts as a strong path for generating foreign exchange. India is one among the most admired tourist destinations in Asia. Tourism is undoubtedly an important area in a country’s economic well-being and development. It supports in the socio, cultural and economic prosperity by attracting the foreign money to the country, thus leads to the overall development of the economy. Tourism today is a crucial factor in world trade with international and multi-faceted dimensions as a means

of earning foreign exchange, as a provider of employment and as a powerful tool of development.

Job satisfaction is the extent of positive feelings or attitudes that individuals possess with their jobs. If he likes his job very much, he will experience greater job satisfaction. The major factors that influence personnel satisfaction are compensation package, promotion chances, training, scientific work tasks, relationship with co-workers and supervisors, and the appreciation for good work. The immediate concern of human resource management is finding the ways and means of ensuring employee satisfaction with the ultimate goal of bringing out the best in the human resource of any industry. Happy workers are productive workers and productive workers are likely to be happy. Personnel satisfaction is important to face the challenges of maintaining productivity of the firm by holding their personnel consistently engaged and motivated. Changing need of personnel together with the rising health costs and various problems of the workforce also pose a challenge for the management. By creating a work environment that maintains personnel satisfaction, the management can motivate people towards exceptional performance at the workplace.

2. Tourism in Kerala

Kerala is a green strip of land, a true natural beauty in the south west corner of Indian peninsula also named globally as “God’s Own Country”. Its unique features were not limited to its calm climate, a long shoreline with peaceful beaches, mild stretches of emerald backwaters, green hill stations and exotic wildlife, waterfalls, plantations and paddy fields, very famous ayurvedic treatments, varied art forms, magnetic festivals, monuments and mouth-watering cuisine make Kerala a unique experience for all. This tropical paradise with its spectacular and varied natural attractions has largely attracted holiday planners from across the globe. Realising the significance of tourism in improving the economic development of the state, the Government of Kerala in 1986 declared tourism as an industry. Today, tourism is Kerala's rapid booming industry and one

of the fastest growing, high income generating and employment creating area. The Kerala State Tourism Development Corporation along with private entrepreneurs is taking varied steps to develop the infrastructure and other allied facilities at places with tourism potential.

3. Rivers, lakes and beaches for tourism business

In Kerala, there are 44 rivers; out of this 41 originate from the Western Ghats region on the east of the state and flow westward to reach the Lakshadweep Sea. The remaining three rivers which include the Kabbini, Bhavani and Pambar originate from the Western Ghats and flow towards the east and reach the Bay of Bengal, which flows through the neighbouring states. The Vembanad Lake which is considered to be the most important of the west coast canal system has a length of 84 km and an average breadth of 3.1 km. It covers an area of 204 square kilometre stretching from Alappuzha to Kochi. Pathiramanal, the mysterious sand of midnight, having coconut palms and luxuriant vegetation is situated in the centre of this lake. Perumbalam and Pallippuram are very important islands in this lake. The Thannermukkom regulator constructed across Vembanad Lake between Thannermukkom and Vechur is intended to prevent tidal action and intrusion of saline water into the lake. It is the largest mud regulator in India.

Table 1

Distribution of Coastline in Kerala (District Wise)

S.No.	District	Length of Coast line	
		Length (Km)	% of Total
1	Thiruvananthapuram	78	13.22
2	Kollam	37	6.27
3	Alappuzha	82	13.9
4	Ernakulam	46	7.8
5	Thrissur	54	9.15
6	Malappuram	70	11.87
7	Kozhikode	71	12.03
8	Kannur	82	13.9
9	Kasargode	70	11.86
	Total	590	100

Source: Kerala State Council for Science, Technology, Environment.

In Kerala, almost all of the resorts, homestays, hotels lie near to any of these natural gifts, some lies near beaches while some other near lakes/rivers. Hence, these natural beauties have immense role in the tourism sector in Kerala State and especially in the case of Alappuzha district of Kerala state which is the study area. A need was felt to analyse the personnel satisfaction with the resorts of Alappuzha district of Kerala.

4. Review of literature

Koh and Boo (2004) found a significant and positive relationship between ethical culture and job satisfaction, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The study points out that organizational ethics can be used as a way to develop good organizational outcomes.

Bjerke, et al. (2007) found a strong connection between artefacts and identity, creativity, employee satisfaction, motivation and mood was established. Aesthetics seemed to be significant as there is lot of face-to-face interaction between the prospective customers and employees of the business firm.

Antoncic and Antoncic (2011) analysed a positive relationship between personnel satisfaction, intrapreneurship and development. Age is the influential variable among all the variables under the study.

Pelit, et al. (2011) found that the relationships with the co-workers and physical conditions are considered to be the mostly influencing positive aspects related to job satisfaction, while unfair pay package is the negative factor related to job satisfaction. The correlation and regression analyses point out that psychological and behavioural empowerment has an important role on the job satisfaction.

Paco and Nave (2013) showed that the volunteers' experience is satisfactory and has a positive relation with the feelings of happiness. The relationship between volunteers' satisfaction and motivation found to be weak.

5. Need and significance

To explain the importance of personnel satisfaction, it is better to quote a popular saying “happy workers are productive workers and productive workers are likely to be happy”. Success of every firm truly lies with how much their employees are ready to work for them. Only when an employee is satisfied with the working environment and job, he/she does, the firm can say they are moving towards glory. But, as we always say, men are considered to be the most flexible yet complex factor to control. By properly controlling human resource, every firm can reach its goal with easiness. A need was felt to analyse the level of personnel satisfaction in resorts of Alappuzha district, Kerala as this place is very famous for tourism and approximately 24 resorts are there in this small district itself. It is much significant to study the major problems faced by the employees of these resorts and also to know how well they are treated by the management of these resorts.

6. Objectives of the study

1. To find out the job satisfaction level of employees working in various resorts in Alappuzha district, Kerala.
2. To analyse the quality of working environment in various resorts under study.
3. To study the factors of job satisfaction of employees working in tourism sector, especially in resorts.
4. To find out the problems faced by the employees working in the resorts of Alappuzha district, Kerala.

7. Research methodology

For this study, both primary and secondary data were used. Schedule method was used for collecting data from the employees to analyse the

satisfaction level. Convenience sampling method is used for selecting the samples. The researchers selected 5 different resorts (2 lake side resorts and 3 beach resorts) in Alappuzha district. From these resorts, 140 employees were selected, which includes 35 supervisors and 105 employees. For data analysis, simple percentage analysis was used.

8. Data analysis

Table 2

Working Environment Parameters

Q. No.	Employees (105)										Supervisors (35)									
	SDA		DA		N		A		SA		SDA		DA		N		A		SA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
W ₁	0	0	2	2	29	28	74	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	10	30	87	1	3
W ₂	0	0	0	0	2	2	89	85	14	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	94	2	6
W ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0	84	80	21	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	97	1	3
W ₄	0	0	29	28	63	60	13	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	40	20	57	1	3
W ₅	0	0	3	3	21	20	75	71	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	27	77	8	23
W ₆	0	0	4	4	21	20	80	76	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	32	91	2	6
W ₇	0	0	0	0	0	0	99	94	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	31	89
W ₈	0	0	29	28	63	60	13	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	40	13	38	8	22
W ₉	0	0	80	76	21	20	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	89	4	11
W ₁₀	0	0	0	0	21	20	71	68	13	12	4	11	13	37	9	26	9	26	0	0
W ₁₁	0	0	8	8	63	60	34	32	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	57	7	20	8	23
W ₁₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	90	86	15	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	40	21	60
W ₁₃	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	101	96	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	89	4	11
W ₁₄	0	0	0	0	0	0	86	82	19	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	97	1	3

SDA-Strongly Disagree; DA- Disagree; N- Neutral; A- Agree; SA-Strongly Agree

Table 3

Job Parameters

Q. No.	Employees (105)										Supervisors (35)									
	SDA		DA		N		A		SA		SDA		DA		N		A		SA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
J ₁	0	0	0	0	0	0	92	88	13	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	31	89
J ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	97	92	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	97	1	3
J ₃	11	10	88	84	6	6	0	0	0	0	18	51	14	40	3	9	0	0	0	0
J ₄	0	0	0	0	34	32	67	64	4	4	8	23	26	74	1	3	0	0	0	0
J ₅	0	0	0	0	0	0	78	74	27	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	31	89
J ₆	0	0	0	0	21	20	63	60	21	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	14	30	86
J ₇	0	0	0	0	13	12	84	80	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	69	11	31
J ₈	0	0	0	0	48	46	55	52	2	2	6	17	20	57	7	20	2	6	0	0

J ₉	0	0	0	0	17	16	71	68	17	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	86	5	14
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SDA-Strongly Disagree; DA- Disagree; N- Neutral; A- Agree; SA-Strongly Agree

Table 4

Satisfaction Parameters

Q. No.	Employees (105)										Supervisors (35)									
	VDS		DS		N		S		HS		VDS		DS		N		S		HS	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
S ₁	0	0	0	0	8	8	13	12	84	80	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	6	33	94
S ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	84	80	21	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	89	4	11
S ₃	16	15	84	80	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	91	3	9
S ₄	0	0	19	18	63	60	19	18	4	4	0	0	1	3	4	11	30	86	0	0
S ₅	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	96	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	91	3	9
S ₆	0	0	26	25	47	45	32	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	9	32	91
S ₇	0	0	29	28	63	60	13	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	89	4	11
S ₈	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	96	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	89	4	11
S ₉	0	0	0	0	21	20	84	80	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	91	3	9

VDS-Very Dissatisfied; DS- Dissatisfied; N- Neutral; S-Satisfied; HS-Highly Satisfied

9. Findings

By analyzing the working environment parameter, W1 indicates that majority of the employees and supervisory staff agrees that the management considers employee’s need while planning work schedules. W2 states that both the employees and supervisory staff have the opinion that in order to solve problems arising out of customers, management work together with them. All the employees and supervisory staff are of the opinion that the inter-department training provided helps them in doing other job as well, also it should be noted that a good portion of employees strongly agree to the statement W3 specified the importance of inter-department training. More than half of supervisors agree that the management shares information regarding competitors’ innovative strategies and plans with them whereas employees had a distinct view about it. Majority of them had a neutral response and about one third of the respondents disagree to the statement W4. Supervisors are motivated to ask any doubts regarding their work for their improvement as the analysis shows that majority of them agree and rest portion strongly agree to the statement W5 whereas, majority of the employees

have a neutral response. When analyzing W6, in order to solve problems, management asks supervisors for their opinion as majority of the respondents agree to that statement whereas management considers the opinion of a small portion of employees for solving any issues arising to the resort as only a small portion of employees agree to that statement; majority of them had a neutral response and a small portion even disagree to the statement. Both the employees' category was very impressed about the orientation provided by the management; a good portion of supervisors strongly agree to the statement W7 concerning the orientation given by the management of resort.

When asked about the freedom of doing the work, majority of the respondents have a neutral response; even a small portion of employees disagree to the statement W8; specifying freedom of doing work. The employees are not much satisfied about the workload provided as majority (76%) of them disagrees to the statement W9; whereas majority of the supervisors agree that they are given only reasonable workload. There is a dispersed agreement level among the supervisors with regard to the statement W10 which shows the employees' relationship with their colleagues; whereas majority of employees was having a positive impression about the relations among the colleagues even though a small portion has a neutral response towards the W10. Both the employee category has a neutral response towards the W11 showing the level of inter-department communication even though less than a half of supervisors says that they have a good level of inter-department communication. W12 interprets that all most all of the supervisory staff are very much satisfied about the management's way of admiring things when they do something good in the resort. Majority of the employees agree to W13 that hard work was much appreciated by the management by providing enough chances of promotions. With regard to the safety features provided by management to the employees, all the employees are satisfied as majority of them agree to the W14 and a small portion of employees strongly agree to that.

The analysis of job parameter, almost all of the employees are ready to take any job assignments allotted to them as majority of the employees agree and that of supervisors strongly agree to J1. It is noted that majority of employees were willing to work for this resort with much effort than what is actually expected by analyzing the J2 as majority agree to the statement concerning it. Both the employees and supervisors have the opinion that they are having good level of loyalty towards the resort as they disagreed to a negative statement J3 which specifies about the employees' loyalty even though a small portion of employees had a neutral response. J4 specifies that employees do often face difficulties in accepting the policies and plans framed out by the management whereas an opposite response is being made by the supervisors. J5 analysed how much proud the employees for being an employee for the particular resort and it is found that majority of employees agree and supervisors strongly agree to the statement. The statement J6 which analysed the response to that the statement "resort really inspires the best in them in terms of job performance"; majority of supervisors strongly agree and employees agree showing that supervisors are much inspired that employees even though both the categories are inspired to a good level. Majority of respondents feel very happy that they chose to work in this resort over its competitors when analysing J7. For the statement J8, more than just a half of employees agree and another large portion have a neutral response whereas majority of supervisors disagree to this negative statement showing their willingness/acceptability towards their willingness to work for a long with this resort. Majority of the supervisors are much concerned about the future of resort whereas a small portion of employees have a neutral response even though majority of them had agreed to J9.

By analyzing the satisfaction parameter, S1 specifies that majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with the opportunities for career advancement. Both the employees and supervisors were satisfied with the attitude of their supervisors and management as per the analysis of S2. The statement S3 analyses the satisfaction towards pay package and it is inferred that majority of supervisors

were satisfied with the pay package whereas majority of employees were very dissatisfied with the pay package they receive. About the relationship with co-workers, S4 states that majority of employees were having a neutral satisfaction even though there are a small portion who is satisfied and dissatisfied whereas with regard to supervisors, majority of them were satisfied with the relationship with co-workers. S5 analysed about the satisfaction level on job type that do in a daily basis and majority of employees were satisfied. About the satisfaction level on training (S6), majority of supervisors were satisfied whereas with regard to employees, majority of them were having a neutral response and even a small portion was dissatisfied with the training they get. S7 analysed about the satisfaction level on performance evaluation methods and it is found out that supervisors were satisfied with that whereas employees are not that satisfied with performance evaluation method as majority of respondents are having a neutral response and some other portion specified dissatisfied as their response. Majority of the employees were satisfied with tools/equipment/materials provided by management to do work as per S8. As per S9, majority of the supervisors were satisfied with other financial benefits, while 20% of the employees have a neutral level of satisfaction even though majority of them were satisfied.

10. Conclusion

It is vital that all organization should keep an eye on the personnel satisfaction as employees are considered to be the most important element in every organization. If the personnel of an organization are satisfied with their job and their working environment, they will definitely work hard for the organization thus, the organization itself as whole develops. It is necessary for every type of firms to keep their employees satisfied by providing all benefits and other resources in a way acceptable to them. The results of study highlighted many positives and negatives of the resorts under study. The management should take necessary steps to solve these issues which the study highlights. It is advisable that management should try to participate the employees in solving problems arising in the firm, so that they develop a sense of commitment and wantedness. Another

important negative that highlighted in the study is to change/improve the performance evaluation method of lower level employees of the firms under study. Almost all the lower level employees are dissatisfied with the pay package and workload they receive, so management should take reasonable steps to rethink about the problem mentioned. Even though the employees face some problems from the management, all of them were very proud to be the employees of the organization, that itself a great thing for the management to have a self-applause. It is better to have a screening on the problems faced by the lower level employees so that the management will be able to bring more positive benefits by improving satisfaction level of employees.

11. Reference

- Arminda do Paço., & Ana Claudia Nave (2013). Corporate volunteering: A case study centred on the motivations, satisfaction and happiness of company employees. *Employee Relations*, 35 (5), 547-559.
- Dhavamani, K., & Natarajan, C. (2020). Job Satisfaction of employees in JSW Steel Limited, Salem Works. *Studies in Indian Place Names*, 40 (13), 1131-1138.
- Elbeyi Pelit., Yuksel Oztürk., & Yağın Arslanturk (2011). The effects of employee empowerment on employee job satisfaction: A study on hotels in Turkey. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 23 (6), 784-802.
- Hian Chye Koh., & El'fred H.Y. Boo (2004). Organisational ethics and employee satisfaction and commitment. *Management Decision*, 42 (5), 677-693.
- Natarajan, C., & Mayandi, K. (2019). Service quality of tour operators in Yercaud Hill Station: Empirical assessment. *Inspira-Journal of Commerce, Economics & Computer Science*, 7 (3), 213-217.
- Rune Bjerke., Nicholas Ind., & Donatella De Paoli (2007). The impact of aesthetics on employee satisfaction and motivation. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 2 (1), 57-73.

12. Appendix

Statements Used in Questionnaire

Q. No.	Working Environment Parameters:
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W ₁	Employees' needs were considered by the management while planning work schedules.
W ₂	To solve problems from customer's side, management and employees work together.
W ₃	Inter-department training was provided for employees to do other jobs.
W ₄	Management shares information about competitor's innovative strategies and polices with employees.
W ₅	Employees were motivated to ask any information to the management for doing their job better.
W ₆	To solve problems, management asks employees about their opinions.
W ₇	Management provides good orientation to their employees for doing their job better.
W ₈	Employees were given enough freedom to do their work in the way they like.
W ₉	Employees were given only reasonable workload.
W ₁₀	Employees keep a good relationship with their colleagues.
W ₁₁	Inter-department communication was good and effective.
W ₁₂	Management admires and supports employees when their work is in some way outstanding.
W ₁₃	Hardworking employees are appreciated by providing opportunities for promotion.
W ₁₄	Management takes every step for creating a safe environment for their employees.
Q. No.	Job Parameters:
J ₁	I am ready to take any type of job assignments in order to keep working for this resort.
J ₂	I am willing to work for this resort with much effort than what is actually expected.
J ₃	I am having very little loyalty to this resort.
J ₄	I often face difficulties in accepting the policies and plans relating to its employees.
J ₅	I feel proud to tell others that I am an employee of this resort.
J ₆	This resort really inspires the best in me in terms of job performance.
J ₇	I feel very happy that I chose to work in this resort over its competitors.
J ₈	I think I cannot gain much by staying here for long.
J ₉	I am much concerned about the future of this resort.
Q. No.	Satisfaction Parameters:
S ₁	Opportunities for career advancement.

S ₂	Attitude of supervisors and superiors.
S ₃	Pay Package
S ₄	Relationship with Co-workers.
S ₅	Job type that you do in a daily basis.
S ₆	Training.
S ₇	Performance Evaluation Methods.
S ₈	Tools/Equipment/Materials provided by management to do your work.
S ₉	Other financial benefits (retirement plan, housing & fuel allowance etc.)